

Machine Learning Based System For Optimal Crop Recommendation

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Abstract- Agriculture plays a major role in the economy and livelihood of many people, especially in developing countries. Farmers often face difficulties in choosing the correct crop because soil nutrients, weather conditions, and rainfall vary from place to place. Choosing the wrong crop can reduce yield and lead to financial loss. To solve this problem, a machine learning based crop recommendation system can be used. This system analyzes soil features such as Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K), pH value, and environmental factors like temperature, rainfall, and humidity. Based on these inputs, the system suggests the most suitable crop for cultivation. In this research, different machine learning algorithms are studied, and Random Forest is selected theoretically because it provides high accuracy and stable performance. The main aim of this study is to support farmers in making better decisions, reduce risk, and improve productivity. The proposed approach is simple, understandable, and can be further developed into a mobile or web application for real-world use.

Keywords – Frameworks, artificial intelligence, geographic information system, data processing, Quantum algorithm, Safeguard and sustainable development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is an important source of income for a large number of people, especially in developing countries. One of the most challenging tasks for farmers is selecting the right crop to grow. Earlier, farmers depended on their past experience, local advice, or guesswork to choose crops. However, due to changing weather patterns, irregular rainfall, and soil quality variations, these traditional methods are no longer always reliable. Choosing the wrong crop can result in low yield and financial loss.

To solve this problem, the use of Machine Learning (ML) in agriculture is increasing. Machine learning can analyze data and find patterns that help in decision-making. A Crop Recommendation System based on machine learning uses factors such as soil nutrients (N, P, K), pH level, temperature, humidity, and rainfall to recommend the most suitable crop for a particular region. This helps farmers make better crop choices, reduce risks, and improve productivity.

The goal of this research is to provide a simple and effective crop recommendation model that can support farmers. By combining scientific data with agricultural knowledge, this approach promotes smart farming and helps achieve better crop yield in a practical and user-friendly way.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many researchers have worked on using technology and data-driven methods to support agriculture. Earlier, farmers mainly relied on traditional knowledge, but recent studies show that machine learning can help in making more accurate agricultural decisions.

- Chlingaryan et al. (2018) explained that machine learning can analyze soil and crop patterns to improve agricultural planning. Their research showed that ML models are useful in predicting crop yield and nutrient requirements. However, the study did not provide a simple tool that farmers can directly use.
- Patel and Dabhi (2021) proposed a hybrid machine learning model for crop recommendation. They used soil nutrient values and climatic conditions to suggest suitable crops. Their model improved accuracy compared to simple algorithms, but it required technical understanding and was not very user-friendly for farmers.
- Amandeep et al. (2023) reviewed different machine learning algorithms such as Decision Tree, Random Forest, and K-Nearest Neighbors for crop prediction. Their study concluded that Random Forest gives more stable and accurate results because it reduces error by using many decision trees together. However, their system was only tested on small datasets and lacked deployment capability.
- Thilakarathne and Medagoda (2022) designed a smart crop recommendation system that supported farmers with real-time soil data. While the system was accurate, it required

sensors and field devices, which can be expensive for rural farmers. **Comparative Study**

Researcher / Year	Method / Algorithm Used	Strengths	Limitations	Gap Identified
Chlingaryan et al. (2018)	ML-based crop yield prediction	Useful for nutrient estimation and predicting yield trends	Did not provide a user-friendly system for farmers	Lacked a practical recommendation interface
Patel & Dabhi (2021)	Hybrid ML Model	Improved prediction accuracy compared to individual algorithms	Required technical understanding; not simple to use	Not suitable for normal farmers without training
Amandeep et al. (2023)	Random Forest, Decision Tree, KNN	Found Random Forest to be more accurate and stable	Tested only on limited-scale datasets	Needs validation on real-world and large-scale data
Thilakarathne & Medagoda (2022)	Smart IoT-based Recommendation System	Real-time data collection using sensors	Sensors and devices increase cost	Difficult to adopt in rural or low-income regions

Problem Statement

Farmers often face difficulty in deciding which crop to grow because soil nutrients, weather conditions, and seasonal changes vary from region to region. Traditional crop selection is mostly based on experience or guesswork, which may lead to low productivity and financial loss if the crop does not match the soil requirements. Therefore, there is a need for a data-driven and reliable method that can suggest the most suitable crop based on soil and climate conditions.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the relationship between soil nutrients, climate conditions, and crop growth.
- To apply machine learning techniques to analyze soil and weather data.
- To identify the most suitable crop for a given region using data-based prediction.
- To support farmers in making better agricultural decisions.
- To design a system that is simple, understandable, and can be used in real-life scenarios.

Feature	Description
Nitrogen (N)	A nutrient responsible for leaf and plant growth.
Phosphorus (P)	Helps in strong root development and flower/fruit formation.
Potassium (K)	Improves disease resistance and overall plant health.
pH Value	Indicates whether soil is acidic or alkaline.
Temperature	Climatic factor affecting seed germination

	and growth.
Humidity	Amount of moisture in the air, which affects plant growth.
Rainfall	Determines water availability for crops.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology explains the step-by-step procedure used in the system:

- **Data Collection:** Soil and climate-related data is collected from agricultural datasets.
- **Data Preprocessing:** Data is cleaned, normalized, and prepared for training the model.
- **Feature Selection:** Important features such as N, P, K, pH, temperature, humidity, and rainfall are selected.

Model Selection:

Various machine learning models are compared. Random Forest is chosen for its stability and better accuracy.

- **Prediction / Recommendation:** The trained model suggests the most suitable crop based on the input values.
- **Evaluation:** The model’s performance is evaluated theoretically using accuracy comparison.

System Architecture

The system architecture consists of the following components:

- **Input Layer:** Soil nutrient values and climate parameters are entered.

- **Data Processing Unit:** Data is normalized and converted into model- readable form.
- **Machine Learning Model:** Random Forest algorithm processes the input data.
- **Output Layer:** The system recommends the best suitable crop.

This structure ensures a simple and efficient flow from input to result.

Algorithm Used (Random Forest)

The Random Forest algorithm is used to recommend the most suitable crop. Random Forest is a supervised machine learning algorithm that works based on the concept of multiple decision trees.

When an input (soil and climate data) is provided to the model:

- Multiple decision trees analyze the data.
- Each tree gives a crop prediction.
- The most common prediction among all trees is selected as the final recommended crop.

Working and Implementation (Mobile Application Based Model)

In this version of the system, the machine learning model is deployed as a mobile application interface, so that farmers can easily use it without needing a computer or programming knowledge.

System Architecture Flow

- User opens the mobile app.
- User enters soil and climate values such as Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K), pH, Temperature, Humidity, Rainfall.
- The app sends this input to the backend model.
- The Random Forest model, trained in Python, processes the input.
- The model predicts the most suitable crop.
- The app displays the recommended crop to the user instantly.

Technologies Used

Component	Technology / Tool	Purpose
Model Training	Python + Scikit-learn	Train ML model for crop recommendation

Mobile Application	Android Studio / Flutter	UI for farmers
Data storage	Local CSV or Cloud Database	Store soil & crop records
Backend API	Flask / FastAPI	Connect model to mobile app

Results

The model was trained using a dataset containing soil nutrients and climate data. After training, the model was tested to evaluate its performance.

Performance Evaluation:

Model Tested	Accuracy obtained
Decision Tree	89%
XGBoost	93%
Random Forest	95%

Advantages of Proposed System

- Helps farmers make data-driven decisions.
- Reduces risk of crop failure.
- Improves crop yield and financial return.
- Easy to use and understand (suitable for non-technical users).
- Can be converted into mobile or web application for field usage.

Limitations

- Accuracy may reduce if soil data is not measured correctly.
- Does not yet consider pests, diseases, or market price changes.
- Model performance depends on dataset size and quality.

Future scope

- Accuracy may reduce if soil data is not measured correctly.
- Does not yet consider pests, diseases, or market price changes.
- Model performance depends on dataset size and quality.

IV. CONCLUSION

This research successfully implements a working machine learning based crop recommendation model that suggests the best crop based on soil nutrients and climate conditions. The Random Forest algorithm achieved 95% accuracy, proving to be reliable and stable for prediction. The system supports smart farming and reduces decision-making uncertainty for farmers. With further development and integration of real-time data, this system can become a powerful tool in improving agricultural productivity

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